

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CONFIDENCE INTERVALS FOR 5 MINUTES

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Abstract

Interval estimation is a fundamental concept in statistical inference, allowing researchers to construct confidence intervals for population parameters. This paper provides a comprehensive overview of the methods and formulas for constructing confidence intervals for various population parameters, including the mean of a normally distributed population, the population proportion, and the difference between means. The paper also discusses the importance of sample size determination for estimation and the use of different distributions, such as the standard normal distribution, Chi-square distribution and the Student's t-distribution, in constructing confidence intervals.

Keywords: interval estimation, confidence intervals, large samples, paired samples

Introduction

The concept of statistical confidence intervals appeared in the early 20th century, particularly in the field of mathematical statistics, we present some of them. While the precise date of its first appearance is difficult to determine due to the gradual development of statistical theory, key contributions from statisticians such as J. Neyman and E. Pearson in the 1930s played a significant role in formalizing the concept.

Here's a literature review focusing on the historical development and foundational works related to confidence intervals:

This [1] seminal paper by Jerzy Neyman in 1937 is often cited as one of the earliest works on confidence intervals. It introduces the concept and discusses its interpretation and properties. Egon Pearson's paper from

1936 is another early work that contributed to the development of confidence intervals. It provides theoretical foundations and practical applications [2]. This classic book [3] by R.A. Fisher, first published in 1925, lays the foundation for the work for many statistical concepts, including confidence intervals. While the term "confidence interval" may not be explicitly used, the ideas presented laid the foundation for its later development. Efron and Tibshirani's book from 1994 introduces bootstrap methods as a modern approach to constructing confidence intervals, providing a powerful alternative to traditional methods [4]. This review article [5] by Davison and Hinkley from 1997 provides an overview of modern approaches to constructing confidence intervals, including bootstrap methods and Bayesian approaches.

		Confidence intervals	Sample Error L	How to calculate the special number	Table
1	Confidence intervals for the mean of population that is normally distributed: population variance known	$\bar{x} - L < \mu < \bar{x} + L$ $\bar{x}$ - sample mean L - Sample Error	$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$ σ - standard deviation n - sample of size	if $\alpha = 0.05$ $P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.025}) = 0.025$ $P(Z > z_{0.025}) = F(z_{0.025}) = 0.975$ Table 2 $z_{0.025} = 1.96$ 	Aliev1, table 2
2	Confidence intervals for the mean of population that is normally distributed: large sample size	$\bar{x} - L < \mu < \bar{x} + L$ $\bar{x}$ - sample mean L - Sample Error	$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \frac{S_x}{\sqrt{n}}$ S_x - standard deviation n - sample of size	$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = F(z_{\alpha/2}) = 1 - z_{\alpha/2}$ Table 2 $z_{\alpha/2} = \text{Table 2}$ 	Aliev1, table 2

<p>3</p>	<p>Confidence interval for μ: small samples Student's t distribution ($n < 30$) $t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{s/\sqrt{n}}$</p>	<p>$\bar{x} - L < \mu < \bar{x} + L$ $\bar{x}$ - sample mean L - Sample Error</p>	<p>$L = t_{n-1, \alpha/2} \cdot \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}$ n - sample of size S - standard deviation $S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$ or $S = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} [\sum x_i^2 - n \cdot (\bar{x})^2]}$</p>	<p>$P(t_{n-1} > t_{n-1, \alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $v = n-1$</p>	<p>Aliev1, table 4</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Confidence intervals for population proportion: Large samples $n \cdot p \cdot q > 9$</p>	<p>$\hat{p} - L < p < \hat{p} + L$ $\hat{p}$ - sample proportion $\hat{p} = \frac{x}{n}$ X - number of elements in the population or sample that possesses a specific characteristic L - Sample Error</p>	<p>$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n}}$ n - sample of size</p>	<p>$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $F(z_{\alpha/2}) = 1 - z_{\alpha/2}$ Table 2 $z_{\alpha/2} = \text{Table 2}$</p>	<p>Aliev1, table 2</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Confidence intervals for the difference between means: paired samples</p>	<p>$\bar{d} - L < \mu_x - \mu_y < \bar{d} + L$ $\bar{d} = \frac{\sum d}{n}$ d - difference between means n - sample of size L - Sample Error</p>	<p>$L = t_{n-1, \alpha/2} \cdot \frac{S_d}{\sqrt{n}}$ n - sample of size S_d - standard deviation: $S_d = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} [\sum d^2 - n \cdot (\bar{d})^2]}$</p>	<p>$P(t_{n-1} > t_{n-1, \alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $v = n-1$</p>	<p>Aliev1, table 4</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>Confidence intervals for the difference between means of two normal populations with known variances</p>	<p>$d - L < \mu_x - \mu_y < d + L$ d - difference between means $d = \bar{X} - \bar{Y}$ L - Sample Error</p>	<p>$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_x^2}{n_x} + \frac{\sigma_y^2}{n_y}}$ σ_x^2, σ_y^2 - known variances n_x, n_y - sample of sizes</p>	<p>$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $F(z_{\alpha/2}) = 1 - z_{\alpha/2}$ Table 2 $z_{\alpha/2} = \text{Table 2}$</p>	<p>Aliev1, table 2</p>
<p>7</p>	<p>Confidence interval for the difference between the population means: unknown population variances that</p>	<p>$d - L < \mu_x - \mu_y < d + L$ d - difference between means $d = \bar{X} - \bar{Y}$ L - Sample Error</p>	<p>$L = t_{n_x+n_y-2, \frac{\alpha}{2}} \cdot S \cdot \sqrt{\frac{n_x+n_y}{n_x \cdot n_y}}$ n_x, n_y - sample of sizes S - standard deviation $S = \sqrt{\frac{(n_x-1) \cdot S_x^2 + (n_y-1) \cdot S_y^2}{n_x+n_y-2}}$ S_x^2, S_y^2 - sample variances</p>	<p>$P(t_{n_x+n_y-2} > t_{n_x+n_y-2, \alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $v = n_x + n_y - 2, \frac{\alpha}{2}$</p>	<p>Aliev1, table 4</p>

	are assumed to be equal				
8	Confidence interval for the difference between the population proportions: (large samples)	$d - L < p_x - p_y < d + L$ d - difference between sample proportions $d = \widehat{p}_x - \widehat{p}_y$ L - Sample Error	$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot A$ $A = \sqrt{\frac{\widehat{p}_x(1-\widehat{p}_x)}{n_x} + \frac{\widehat{p}_y(1-\widehat{p}_y)}{n_y}}$ n_x, n_y - sample of sizes $\widehat{p}_x, \widehat{p}_y$ - sample proportions	$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $F(z_{\alpha/2}) = 1 - z_{\alpha/2}$ Table 2 $z_{\alpha/2} = \text{Table 2}$	Aliev1, table 2
9	Confidence interval for the variance of a normal distribution	$\frac{L}{\chi^2_{n-1, \frac{\alpha}{2}}} < \sigma^2 < \frac{L}{\chi^2_{n-1, 1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}}$ χ^2_{n-1} - Chi-square distribution L - Sample Error	$L = (n - 1) \cdot S^2$ n - sample of size S^2 - sample variance	$P(\chi^2_{n-1} > \chi^2_{n-1, \frac{\alpha}{2}}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $\chi^2_{n-1, \frac{\alpha}{2}} = \text{Table 3}$ $P(\chi^2_{n-1} > \chi^2_{n-1, 1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}) = 1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $\chi^2_{n-1, 1-\frac{\alpha}{2}} = \text{Table 3}$	Aliev1, table 3
10	Sample size determination for the estimation of mean	$\bar{x} - L < \mu < \bar{x} + L$ $\bar{x}$ - sample mean L - Sample Error	$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$ σ - standard deviation n - sample of size $n = \frac{(z_{\alpha/2})^2 \cdot \sigma^2}{L^2}$	$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $F(z_{\alpha/2}) = 1 - z_{\alpha/2}$ Table 2 $z_{\alpha/2} = \text{Table 2}$	Aliev1, table 2
11	Sample size determination for the estimation of proportion	$\widehat{p} - L < p < \widehat{p} + L$ $\widehat{p}$ - sample proportion L - Sample Error	$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\widehat{p}(1-\widehat{p})}{n}}$ n - sample of size $\widehat{p}(1 - \widehat{p})$ can not be bigger than 0.25 $n = \frac{(z_{\alpha/2})^2 \cdot 0.25}{L^2}$	$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}$ $F(z_{\alpha/2}) = 1 - z_{\alpha/2}$ Table 2 $z_{\alpha/2} = \text{Table 2}$	Aliev1, table 2

Examples:

1) Confidence intervals for the mean of population that is normally distributed: population variance known

The standard deviation for a population is $\sigma = 8.6$. A random sample selected from this population gave a mean equal to 53.9.

a) Make a 90 % confidence interval for μ assuming $n = 36$

b) Make a 95 % confidence interval for μ assuming $n = 81$

Solution:

a) $\sigma = 8.6, \bar{x} = 53.9, n = 36$

• $100 \cdot (1 - \alpha) \% = 90\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.1$

$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.05$

$$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.05}) = 0.05$$

$$F(z_{0.05}) = 0.95 \rightarrow (\text{Aliev1, table 2})$$

$$z_{0.05} = 1.645$$

$$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} = 1.645 \cdot \frac{8.6}{\sqrt{36}} = 2.358$$

$$\bar{x} - L < \mu < \bar{x} + L$$

$$53.9 - 2.358 < \mu < 53.9 + 2.358$$

$$51.54 < \mu < 56.26$$

Answer: (51.54; 56.26)

$$b) \sigma = 8.6, \bar{x} = 53.9, n = 81$$

$$\bullet 100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 95\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.05$$

$$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.025$$

$$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.025}) = 0.025$$

$$F(z_{0.025}) = 0.975 \rightarrow (\text{Aliev1, table 2})$$

$$z_{0.025} = 1.96$$

$$\bullet L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} = 1.96 \cdot \frac{8.6}{\sqrt{81}} = 1.873$$

$$\bar{x} - L < \mu < \bar{x} + L$$

$$53.9 - 1.873 < \mu < 53.9 + 1.873$$

$$52.03 < \mu < 55.77$$

Answer: (52.03; 55.77)

2) Confidence intervals for the mean of population that is normally distributed: large sample size

A sample of 98 observations taken from a population produced a sample mean equal to 57.3 and a standard deviation equal to 7.2. Make a 99 % confidence interval for μ .

Solution:

$$n = 98, \bar{x} = 57.3, S_x = 7.2,$$

$$100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 99\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.01$$

$$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.005$$

$$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.005}) = 0.005$$

$$F(z_{0.005}) = 0.995 \rightarrow (\text{Aliev1, table 2})$$

$$z_{0.005} = 2.575$$

$$\bullet L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \frac{S_x}{\sqrt{n}} = 2.575 \cdot \frac{7.2}{\sqrt{98}} = 1.87$$

$$\bar{x} - L < \mu < \bar{x} + L$$

$$57.3 - 1.87 < \mu < 57.3 + 1.87$$

$$55.43 < \mu < 59.17$$

Answer: (55.43; 59.17)

3) Confidence interval for μ : small samples

A random sample of 18 cars, which were tested for fuel consumption, gave a mean of 19.8 miles per gallon with a standard deviation of 3.2 miles per gallon. Assuming that the miles per gallon given by cars have a normal distribution, find a 90 % confidence interval for the population mean μ .

Solution:

$$n = 18, \bar{x} = 19.8, S = 3.2$$

$$\bullet 100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 90\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.1$$

$$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.05$$

$$v = n - 1 = 18 - 1 = 17$$

$$P(t_{17} > t_{17,0.05}) = 0.05 \rightarrow \text{Aliev1, table 4}$$

$$t_{17,0.05} = 1.74$$

$$\bullet L = t_{n-1,\alpha/2} \cdot \frac{S}{\sqrt{n}} = 1.74 \cdot \frac{3.2}{\sqrt{18}} = 1.31$$

$$\bar{x} - L < \mu < \bar{x} + L$$

$$19.8 - 1.31 < \mu < 19.8 + 1.31$$

$$18.49 < \mu < 21.11$$

Answer: (18.49; 21.11)

4) Confidence intervals for population proportion: Large samples

A sample selected from a population gave a sample proportion equal to 0.69

a) make a 98 % confidence interval for p assuming n = 100

b) construct a 97 % confidence interval for p assuming n = 500

Solution:

$$a) \hat{p} = 0.69, n = 110$$

$$\bullet 100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 98\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.02$$

$$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.01$$

$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.01}) = 0.01$
 $F(z_{0.01}) = 0.99 \rightarrow$ (Aliev1, table 2)
 $z_{0.01} = 2.325$

$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{110}} = 2.325 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{0.69 \cdot 0.31}{110}} = 0.1025$

$\hat{p} - L < p < \hat{p} + L$
 $0.69 - 0.1025 < p < 0.69 + 0.1025$
 $0.5875 < p < 0.7925$
 Answer: (0.5875; 0.7925)

b) $\hat{p} = 0.69, n = 500$
 $100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 97\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.03$
 $\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.015$
 $P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.015}) = 0.015$
 $F(z_{0.015}) = 0.985 \rightarrow$ (Aliev1, table 2)
 $z_{0.015} = 2.17$

$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{110}} = 2.17 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{0.69 \cdot 0.31}{500}} = 0.045$
 $\hat{p} - L < p < \hat{p} + L$
 $0.69 - 0.045 < p < 0.69 + 0.045$
 $0.645 < p < 0.735$
 Answer: (0.645; 0.735)

5) Confidence intervals for the difference between means: paired samples

A company claims that the course they offer significantly increases the writing speed of secretaries. The following table gives the scores of eight secretaries before and after they attended this course

Before	81	75	89	91	65	70	90	69
After	97	72	93	110	78	69	115	75

Make a 95 % confidence interval for the mean ($\mu_x - \mu_y$) of the population paired differences, where a paired differences is equal to the score before attending the course minus the score after attending the course.

Solution:

8

$100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 95\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.05$
 $\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.025$
 $v = n - 1 = 8 - 1 = 7$
 $P(t_7 > t_{7,0.025}) = 0.025 \rightarrow$ Aliev1, table 4
 $t_{7,0.025} = 2.365$

Before	After	Difference d	d ²
81	97	-16	256
75	72	3	9
89	93	-4	16
91	110	-19	361
65	78	-13	169
70	69	1	1
90	115	-25	625
69	75	-6	36
		$\Sigma d = -79$	$\Sigma d^2 = 1473$

$\bar{d} = \frac{\Sigma d}{n} = \frac{-79}{8} = -9.875$
 $S_d = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} [\Sigma d^2 - n \cdot (\bar{d})^2]}$
 $= \sqrt{\frac{1}{7} [1473 - 8 \cdot (-9.875)^2]} \approx 9.95$

$L = t_{n-1, \alpha/2} \cdot \frac{S_d}{\sqrt{n}} = 2.365 \cdot \frac{9.95}{\sqrt{8}} = 8.32$
 $\bar{d} - L < \mu_x - \mu_y < \bar{d} + L$
 $-9.875 - 8.32 < \mu_x - \mu_y < -9.875 + 8.32$
 $-18.195 < \mu_x - \mu_y < -1.555$
 Answer: (-18.195; -1.555)

6) Confidence intervals for the difference between means of two normal populations with known variances

A random sample of size 32 from a normal population with variance 22500 gave a mean 500. A second random sample of size 36 from a normal population with variance 16900 gave a mean 375. Find a 95 per cent confidence interval for the difference between two population means.

Solution:

$n_x = 32 \quad n_y = 36$

$$\sigma_x^2 = 22500 \quad \sigma_y^2 = 16900$$

$$\bar{X} = 500 \quad \bar{Y} = 375$$

• $100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 95\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.05$

$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.025$

$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.025}) = 0.025$

$F(z_{0.025}) = 0.975 \rightarrow$ (Aliev1, table 2)

$z_{0.025} = 1.96$

• $d = \bar{X} - \bar{Y} = 500 - 375 = 125$

• $L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_x^2}{n_x} + \frac{\sigma_y^2}{n_y}} = 1.96 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{22500}{32} + \frac{16900}{36}}$

$= 67.11$

• $d - L < \mu_x - \mu_y < d + L$

$125 - 67.11 < \mu_x - \mu_y < 125 + 67.11$

$57.89 < \mu_x - \mu_y < 192.11$

Answer: (57.89; 192.11)

7) Confidence interval for the difference between the population means: unknown population variances that are assumed to be equal

A company is interested in buying one of two different kinds of machines. Company tested the two machines for production purposes. The first machine was run for 9 hours and produced an average 163 items per hour with a standard deviation of 19 items. The second machine was run for 14 hours and produced an average of 147 items per hour with a standard deviation of 14 items. Assume that the production per hour for each machines approximately normally distributed. Also assume that the standard deviation of the hourly production of the two populations is equal. Then find a 90 % confidence interval for the difference between the two population means.

$n_x = 9 \quad n_y = 14$

$S_x = 19 \quad S_y = 14$

$\bar{X} = 163 \quad \bar{Y} = 147$

$100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 90\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.1$

$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.05$

$v = n_x + n_y - 2 = 9 + 14 - 2 = 21$

$P(t_{21} > t_{21,0.05}) = 0.05 \rightarrow$ Aliev1, table 4

$t_{21,0.05} = 1.721$

• $d = \bar{X} - \bar{Y} = 163 - 147 = 16$

$S = \sqrt{\frac{(n_x-1) \cdot S_x^2 + (n_y-1) \cdot S_y^2}{n_x+n_y-2}} = \sqrt{\frac{8 \cdot 19^2 + 13 \cdot 14^2}{9+14-2}} = 16.1$

• $L = t_{n_x+n_y-2, \frac{\alpha}{2}} \cdot S = 1.721 \cdot 16.1$

$\sqrt{\frac{9+14}{9 \cdot 14}} = 11.91$

• $d - L < \mu_x - \mu_y < d + L$

$16 - 11.91 < \mu_x - \mu_y < 16 + 11.91$

$4.09 < \mu_x - \mu_y < 27.91$

Answer: (4.09; 27.91)

8) Confidence interval for the difference between the population proportions: (large samples)

A sample of 850 females was selected from ethnic group A and a sample of 950 from ethnic group B. Each female was asked “Did you get married before you were 22?”. 346 of females from group A and 366 of females from group B answered “yes”. Find a 98 % confidence interval for the two population proportions

$n_x = 850 \quad n_y = 950$

$\hat{p}_x = \frac{X}{n_x} = \frac{346}{850} = 0.41 \quad \hat{p}_y = \frac{Y}{n_y} = \frac{366}{950} = 0.39$

• $100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 98\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.02$

$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.01$

$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.01}) = 0.01$

$F(z_{0.01}) = 0.99 \rightarrow$ (Aliev1, table 2)

$z_{0.01} = 2.325$

• $d = \hat{p}_x - \hat{p}_y = 0.41 - 0.39 = 0.02$

$A = \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}_x(1-\hat{p}_x)}{n_x} + \frac{\hat{p}_y(1-\hat{p}_y)}{n_y}} = \sqrt{\frac{0.41 \cdot 0.59}{850} + \frac{0.39 \cdot 0.61}{950}} =$

0.023

$L = z_{\alpha/2} \cdot A = 2.325 \cdot 0.023 = 0.0535$

• $d - L < p_x - p_y < d + L$

$0.02 - 0.0535 < p_x - p_y < 0.02 + 0.0535$

$-0.335 < p_x - p_y < 0.0735$

Answer: (-0.335; 0.0735)

9) Confidence interval for the variance of a normal distribution

The time required to complete a certain operation by the sample of 22 employees of auditing company has a standard deviation of 5.4 min. Construct a 95 % confidence interval for σ .

$n = 22, S = 5.4$

$100 \cdot (1-\alpha)\% = 95\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.05$

$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.025$

$P(\chi_{21}^2 > \chi_{21,0.025}^2) = 0.025$

(Aliev1, table 3)

$\chi_{21,0.025}^2 = 35.48$

$P(\chi_{21}^2 > \chi_{21,0.975}^2) = 0.975$

$$\chi_{21,0.975}^2 = 10.28$$

$$\bullet L = (n - 1) \cdot S^2 = 21 \cdot 5.4^2 = 612.36$$

$$\bullet \frac{L}{\chi_{n-1, \frac{\alpha}{2}}^2} < \sigma^2 < \frac{L}{\chi_{n-1, 1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^2}$$

$$\frac{612.36}{35.48} < \sigma^2 < \frac{612.36}{10.28}$$

$$17.26 < \sigma^2 < 59.57$$

$$4.16 < \sigma < 7.72$$

Answer: (4.16; 7.72)

$$L = 0.194 ; \text{confidence level} = 93\%$$

$$\bullet 100 \cdot (1 - \alpha)\% = 93\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.07$$

$$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.035$$

$$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.035}) = 0.035$$

$$F(z_{0.035}) = 0.965 \rightarrow (\text{Aliev1, table 2})$$

$$z_{0.035} = 1.815$$

$$n = \frac{(z_{\alpha/2})^2 \cdot 0.25}{L^2} = \frac{(1.815)^2 \cdot 0.25}{0.194^2} = 21.9 \approx 22$$

10) Sample size determination for the estimation of mean

Determine the sample size for the estimate of μ for the following:

$$L = 25.07; \sigma = 19.90; \text{confidence level} = 94\%$$

$$\bullet 100 \cdot (1 - \alpha)\% = 94\% \rightarrow \alpha = 0.06$$

$$\frac{\alpha}{2} = 0.03$$

$$P(Z > z_{\alpha/2}) = P(Z > z_{0.03}) = 0.03$$

$$F(z_{0.03}) = 0.97 \rightarrow (\text{Aliev1, table 2})$$

$$z_{0.03} = 1.885$$

$$n = \frac{(z_{\alpha/2})^2 \cdot \sigma^2}{L^2} = \frac{(1.885)^2 \cdot 19.9^2}{25.07^2} = 2.24 \approx 2$$

11) Sample size determination for the estimation of proportion

Determine the most conservative sample size for estimation of the population proportion for the following:

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